

Welcome to Educene

We have entered a new epoch, Educene. This is not a post-Anthropocene transition, where humans mastered the earth with a firm hand. Now the plot becomes more complicated, more subtle: it is no longer human dominance that is at stake, but our connection with artificial intelligence, which insinuates a slow and inexorable transformation. Learning and teaching are no longer simple, direct acts. This relationship with AI disrupts the old order, forcing us to rethink the nature of knowledge. What does it mean to educate, construct and transmit knowledge? In this transition, the feeling is that there are no answers, only growing uncertainty. Yet, it is precisely within this uncertainty, perhaps, that the key lies.

Large global capital and the technologisation of knowledge

We come from the Anthropocene, the Capitalocene, the C(h)thul(h)ucene with the planet reduced to a burning spaceship adrift in space. (Buckminster Fuller, 1968) With the launch of the Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer large language model (LLM) - (GPT, 2022) the modern era closes and the era of Hypermodernity, the Educene, opens. Cassa Depositi e Prestiti Venture Capital + OpenAI have closed a EUR 1 billion agreement to accelerate the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Italy. This agreement aims to strengthen the Italian AI ecosystem, supporting both start-ups and innovative companies, and promoting the adoption and commercialisation of advanced technologies. OpenAI and CDP Venture Capital will collaborate with Italian universities to improve training in the AI sector, creating educational and skills development programmes. Microsoft together with Blackrock announced a EUR 4.2 billion investment in Italy over the next two years, focused on expanding cloud and artificial intelligence (AI) infrastructure. The investment also includes a training plan that aims to improve the digital skills of more than 1 million Italians by the end of 2025. A crucial part of the investment will be allocated to the expansion of the ItalyNorth Cloud Region, which will become one of the main data hubs in Europe, serving not only Italy but also the Mediterranean and North Africa, Microsoft's strategy to create an AI-driven Italian economy expanding into the African continent.

There is something profound at stake. It is a redefinition of the very foundations of our civilisation. The expansion of cloud infrastructure and artificial intelligence, not only in Italy but globally, is not a technical or economic gesture. It is an act that reshapes the structure of society, something that penetrates to its most exposed nerves. We are witnessing a systemic transformation that will go far beyond economics or technology to affect what we consider the home of collective

living: education. How we learn, how we teach, how we imagine: everything will be permeated by this new technological logic. Education, in the modern considered 'the entrance to the house' of the human, will not be sheltered. There will be no more room for teaching as we have known it.

The Artificial Intelligence Aporia

Artificial intelligence represents an unsolvable paradox. On the one hand, it promises to solve energy and environmental problems; on the other, it risks being the downfall. Former Google CEO Eric Schmidt highlighted this dilemma: AI has enormous potential to improve energy efficiency, but its very operation requires huge amounts of energy. In other words, AI could be the key to solving the problem, but only at the cost of ruining the earth through unsustainable energy consumption. For example, large-scale simulations of the human brain require huge amounts of computational power; the Human Brain Project requires 100 million watts and the computational computation of the city of Milan consumes 5,000 megawatts of baseload energy, equivalent to 5 French model nuclear power plants (Pressurised Water Reactor, average capacity ranging between 900 MW and 1,600 MW). This aporia has no solution and, in a sense, must not have one. It is structurally precisely this contradiction that drives us to recover and put critical thinking at the centre: when faced with unsolvable problems, speculation becomes a cultural superstructure. The AI paradox therefore obliges us to think divergently, to construct a learning path based on critical rhetoric. The old adage applies here: we are racing round a corner if we brake now we will get out, because it is in the corner that the solution lies.

The world curve, in doubt accelerates

We find ourselves in the accelerated returns of technology, if once we imagined more than we could create, today we create much more than we can imagine, we are in the midst of an exponential technological curve that is also existential (Anders, 1956). Automation and the unstoppable flow of digital innovations accelerate at a speed that gets out of hand in a breathless race. The pace gives the impression that every decision is a matter of moments, and that each moment exposes us to the risk of falling behind. There is a point beyond which braking too abruptly can be fatal. The risk is loss of control, running off the road (Virilio, 1993). Maintaining the trajectory becomes a matter of a fragile balance between innovation and control. It is in this balance that the future is at stake: in the ability to adapt with lucidity as the world around us curves ever more rapidly.

The multiverse of truths

In the age of Educene, the idea of truth is an archaeological curiosity. There is no single path to knowledge, but a kaleidoscope of worlds in which truths cohabit, often in tension, sometimes in fragile dialogue. While this plurality would once have been considered a symptom of decadence, today it represents our treasure. Knowledge is no longer a monolith rising to dominate the landscape, a path going in only one direction. Reality is too fragmented, too intricate to fit into a single narrative. It is not in the cohesion of ideas that we will find salvation, but in the acceptance of their dispersion. Education can no longer seek definitive answers, a solid home. Rather, it is an exercise in navigation, a cultural nomadism among an infinite number of choices that take us through a multiverse of worldviews. Speculative thinking, in modern ideology much criticised, now becomes the heart of the enterprise. We do not aspire to certainties, but we manage uncertainty, to live with the complexity of exploring borderless territories. The world does not offer a map, but invites us to be cartographers of our exploration, to be aware that truth, if there ever is any, will never be a definitive conquest, but a fleeting, elusive revelation.

The End of the Modern and the Birth of Speculative Education

Hypermodernity has produced a fragmentation and individuation of truths (Stiegler, 2021). Since the 16th century, the centrality of the dialectic reappears (Culianu, 2006). Education cannot lead to a single goal and can only be a dialectic between different truths. *Educere* does not have a single goal, but consists of points of arrival of truth. This is because the aesthetics of victory, the foundation of truth, that was realised after the world wars as a folk-popular form of the ideological framework of human socio-political cultures, collapses because the ideological framework on which it was based no longer exists. Today we have no teleological end point, but indeterminate and recursive global liquid cartographies. Therein lies the imaginary: not so much that of revealing, but of allowing something to reveal itself. The originality of the new is not measured through ideological systems it does not yet possess. Rather, it manifests itself through a selective will, a filter that interposes itself between us and the past - the 20th century with all its labels: modern, colonialist, rational, calculating, platonic, masculine - and the new era that is presenting itself as the 21st century. This filter, while not yet part of the established cultural structure of the new era, is already beginning to shape it, to mould it. In this context, we must apply the rule of the History of Ideas: it is not the explicit content of an era that defines it, nor the ideas it openly expresses. What really distinguishes it is the filter it proposes to read and interpret reality. And the current filter is economic-financial, procedural, automatic, assisted, instantaneous, isomorphic, proactive.

1. **Economic-financial:** The filter of the first twenty-five years of the 21st century is based on the global economy - Vienna School -. The idea that the best way to manage human beings is through economic relations, where life is measured and evaluated in terms of costs, benefits and profits. All decisions are tied to financial dynamics, with the logic of the market as the organising principle.

2. **Procedural:** The process is driven by standardised procedures, making compliance with protocols that guarantee efficiency and replicability essential.

3. **Automatic:** functions, both practical and cognitive, are automatic. Human intervention is an increasing delegation to technology.

4. **Assisted:** Technological assistance is pervasive, from learning to communication, which creates increasing dependence.

5. **Instantaneous:** In a culture that demands immediate gratification, immediacy is the filter. Reflection and planning are replaced by instantaneousness of execution.

6. **Isomorphic:** The filter tends to standardise the forms of expression - writing, images, music, video - are in one platform by integrating different modes of expression in one digital environment.

7. **Proactive:** The proactive filter is characterised by anticipation and prediction of events. It is not a matter of reacting to what happens, but of directing decisions before problems emerge.

The 20th century, with its obsession with absolute truth and closed systems, has passed. Educene demands a radical approach to education, which we call **Speculative Education**. In this model, education is no longer a linear path towards a predefined goal, but an anarchic, open and systemic process, a cultural nomadism where speculation and imagination play a central role. Speculative Education does not provide definitive answers, but invites continuous questioning about the cultural, social and ethical implications of knowledge. It is a model that encourages creativity and critical thinking, prompting students and teachers to explore new horizons and imagine possible futures anarchically (Feyerabend, 1975).

A New Role of Teacher and Student: Cultural Adolescence as Knowledge

In Educene, the role of the teacher changes. He is no longer the holder of knowledge, but a *custodian of past knowledge*, the *keeper of ruins*. Students, on the other hand, are no longer mere receivers of information, but *creators of new narratives*. (Monico, Campagna, 2021) In this

educational paradigm, learning is an open and continuous dialogue in which teachers and students work together to construct new forms of knowledge. The teacher is the guardian of the ruins of the past - the adult- while the student is the one who builds the future - the adolescent- the becoming of the adult. This dynamic and fluid relationship makes it possible to deal with the complexity of the contemporary world, in which knowledge is never fixed, but constantly evolving.

Pragmatics of human education - hypothesis of an rhetorical model

In Educene, students, armed with advanced artificial intelligence such as LLMs, seem reduced to a condition of passivity, seemingly inert users of pre-packaged knowledge. Yet, it is precisely in this passivity that an unexpected critical reaction is hidden. If, as a teacher, I assign a task that I would describe as ‘trinamic’ - requiring the simultaneous search for one meaning and its opposite, or their interdependence - what initially appears as passivity is transformed in the moment of reflection of the output into a complex dialectical process. The output generated by artificial intelligence is no longer a response to be accepted, but rather becomes a catalyst for reflection. In the moment of reception, in careful reading, the student is faced with a double movement: the acceptance of the thesis and the implicit invitation to observe its relationship with the antithesis. It is here that dialectical conflict is engaged, as the machine poses ambivalent questions, and the ‘guardian of the ruins’ - the teacher presiding over the process - demands not a simple acceptance, but a confrontation between the opposing endiadic theses.

This confrontation reveals the new student, who, even when he does not take a position, actually takes a choice that forces him to reflect on omissions. This process activates cognitive and critical participation. The machine produces, the human implies. The machine produces interaction, the human, relation, which is the discourse on interaction. Each iteration leads the student to preach a synthesis, a reflection. In this way, the much-feared passivity turns out to be an unexpected tool: a picklock to unhinge mental habits and create always already new narratives. Education, then, is no longer a process of transmission, but becomes a path of active construction. The interaction with artificial intelligence, seemingly mechanical and impersonal, unexpectedly offers the cue for a deeper exploration of a topic, for a discovery that is personal and intellectually enlivening.

The speculative contribution as an unavoidable challenge

Educene is not a new technological era, but a new way of thinking and practising education. In this context, speculative rhetoric becomes an essential skill to navigate the complex pluriverse of contemporary truths. Our task, as educators and citizens, is to embrace this disorienting criticality.

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